

ISic3004

Votive dedication of Artemidoros

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

base

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found in 1950 near the Chiesa dei Minoritelli , during excavation of the foundations of the Collegio Maria Immacolata (so Manganaro 1961: 191 n.91)

Coordinates

37.504758, 15.082564

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory Not located

Physical Description

A small marble base with a circular depression in the middle of the upper face (10cm in diameter)

Dimensions

Height 7 cm

Width 26 cm

Depth 16 cm

Layout

Text set out over two lines on the front face, the name in line 1 in larger letters

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Lunate epsilon, omega and sigma; mu with full length strokes, all off vertical.

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 15-20 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. Ἀρτεμίδωρος

2. Κλήμεντος δ(οὔλος) οκατ ὄναρ

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro

Translation (en)

Artemidoros, son of Clemens to the fourth generation, (dedicated this) on account of a dream

Commentary

Although seen by Manganaro in the museum at a date no later than 1961, the

stone has not been observed since. In 1961, Manganaro interpreted the δ in line 2 as a numeral, understanding 'son of Klemens to the fourth generation'. In 1988 he tacitly revised this view, interpreting it as an abbreviation for 'slave' instead.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645353

Bibliography

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1962.0388

Manganaro, G. 1961. Ricerche di epigrafia siceliota. I. Per la storia del culto delle divinità orientali in Sicilia. *Siculorum Gymnasium*. 14: 175-198. At 190-191 fig.12

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 49

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